

The Teacher's Knowledge about Special Needs Learners: A Fundamental Element for the Implementation of Inclusive Education

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ABSTRACT: *Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong in Ghana, was one of the pilot institutions that has undertaken inclusive Education programme for students with special needs where students with disabilities (visual impairment, hearing impairment and the physically challenged) learn and share the same facilities with their non-disabled counterparts. Since the pilot project was started in 2003, no systematic study has been carried out to ascertain the extent to which the institution has been able to implement the concept of inclusive education. The aim of the study therefore was to assess Presbyterian College of Education as an inclusive educational institution. A case study design; in which tutors and students at Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong were interviewed, was adopted for the study. A convenience sampling and census techniques were used to recruit 35 students with disabilities and 15 tutors at Presbyterian college of education in the Eastern region of Ghana. In-depth interview and observational techniques were used to assess the views of the participants about inclusive education with regards to teachers' knowledge about how to handle and teach students with special needs. The findings of the study revealed that currently, the teachers have very limited knowledge about how to handle and teach students with special needs. The findings further revealed that generally, the teachers had inadequate understanding of inclusive education before the programme was introduced. Also, lack of preparation on the part of teachers to teach students with special needs was revealed. This is because the teachers' knowledge on the concept of inclusive education is very critical in educating persons with disability. Based on this finding, it is recommended that in-service training should be organised to educate teachers at the College of Education level to facilitate inclusion.*

KEYWORDS: Requisite knowledge, verbalization, Sign language interpreter, illustrations

I. INTRODUCTION

The aim of inclusive education is to ensure that every child of school age is able to access the mainstream school of his or her choice and be able to learn successfully. To this end, the learning needs of all categories of students including those with disabilities need to be addressed. The concept of inclusive education is centered on the fundamental right to education for all as well as the right to non-discrimination and participation (Schultz, 2004). As a result of the World Education Forum, the challenges of getting all children into school has been put on the political agenda in many countries including Ghana and is reflected in Education For All (EFA) National action plans (Avoke, 2001). The Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong, has been one of the first colleges of education in Ghana to practice inclusive education and it has sought to produce better scholars who are visually impaired, hearing impaired and physically challenged. These individuals now stand better chances in life and have benefited a lot from inclusive education as reflected in employment acquisition

(Oppong, 2003). With quality inclusive education, persons with disability can contribute to the socio-economic development of the country.

Inclusive education system requires the adaptation of the general curriculum to make it accessible to all learners; the school's physical environment is to be devoid of any form of disadvantage to all learners, adequate resource room and teachers appropriately trained to meet the needs of all categories of learners. Oppong (2003) stated that inclusive education refers to the adaptation of the school curriculum to make it equally accessible to students with special needs. In inclusive education, the school environment, the climate of the school, and the school plan – are all adapted to suit both able and students with special needs equally. In inclusive education, it is the responsibility of the school to adjust and adapt its environment to suit all categories of students with special needs.

The world declaration on Education for All, states that equal access to education should be provided to all categories of disabled persons. Ghana being a signatory to this declaration is obliged to make attendance of regular schools possible for children with disabilities. Unlike the policy of segregation which separated special needs children from their peers and led to labelling and discrimination, this policy is to allow disabled children attend their neighborhood schools, interact in the society and be participants in the society. This shift in paradigm from segregation to inclusion permits children with special needs to be enrolled full time in regular schools with adequate resource support. This implies that children of mild to moderate special needs will be educated in general schools system alongside their non-disabled counterpart. Prior to the 1990's very few students with disabilities were included in general education classrooms in Ghana. The needs of many of these children were also not met by the Government of Ghana and some parents (Avoke, 2001). Mitchell and Diane (2005) state that providing education to vast number of children with disabilities in regular school poses a number of challenges and issues to be addressed. As such, much attention is not given to issues concerning children with disabilities.

Ghana's educational strategic plan for 2015 was focused on including all persons with disability in the main stream schools by 2015-2016 academic year. As a preparatory strategy, some schools including Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong-Akwapem, were running the inclusive education programme on pilot basis until 2015 when it was fully implemented all over the country. Government is expected to provide equal educational opportunities for children and youth with special needs at pre-tertiary and tertiary levels to promote access and participation, quality and inclusion (National Report, 2004). This implies that as a result of providing education for all children, teachers in general schools must provide instruction and other educational services to meet the needs of a diverse student population. Also, teachers must be prepared to teach all kinds of pupils, including those who present special needs in the classrooms.

Statement of the problem

The right to be educated as stipulated by both international laws and declarations and that of Ghana has made it necessary for the Government of Ghana to provide access to formal education for all school aged children. This does not exclude children with disabilities. In their case, the Government of Ghana and for that matter the education ministry settled for the provision of segregation school for children with disabilities. In effect, special schools such as schools for the blind, schools for the deaf, and schools for the intellectually challenged are dotted around the country. Due to the few number of these schools, the distance between the schools and children with disabilities, coupled with human right issues; thus the right to education, it was agreed at the Salamanca world conference that all children regardless of their disability should be allowed to school in the mainstream system in 2003. The Government of Ghana took up the challenge and began to implement this directive by piloting few schools in the country as inclusive schools. Subsequently, Ghana is now running inclusive education system.

The provisions in the Persons With Disability Act 715 section 17 enjoins the ministry of education to provide the necessary facilities and equipments that enables students with disabilities to benefit from education (Disability Act 715, 2006). Although Presbyterian college of Education is practicing inclusive education, we do not know how effective it is being implemented and the associated constraints to the implementation are also not known. It is not known and clear whether the teachers in the college the required knowledge about inclusive

education. The study is therefore to assess how knowledgeable the teachers are with regards to special needs education at the Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong Akuapem, as an inclusive institution.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Teachers' knowledge about special education needs

Michigan (1991) pictures inclusive education as a system of educating the disabled together with non-disabled students in general schools under general classroom teachers. Kaplan and Ingrid (2013) therefore conclude that the general school teachers need to be trained with the appropriate skills so that they can work better with the disabled students. Similarly, Golder, et al (2005) comment that teachers should be prepared to be able to teach a full range of learners in terms of the diversity of ability, behaviour and social background that they would find in the regular schools.

Understanding the concept of inclusive education

There should be a special educational need element in all courses of initial teacher training which will qualify them to understand their responsibilities under the special education needs code of practice. This will enable teachers to know how to seek advice from specialists on less common types of special education needs to enable teachers differentiate their teaching to meet the needs of all learners (Golder et al., 2005). After their studies about teachers perception on special education needs (Avramidis, Bayliss& Burden, 2000) came to the conclusion that limited information about students with disabilities increase teachers fear, anxiety, and general discomfort in working with these students. Some of these behaviours result from a feeling of lack of preparation for teaching students with disabilities (Cook, 2000).

Similarly, Minchon et al, (2003), thinks challenges will arise if educators do not possess the needed competence in teaching students with special needs and knowledge of strategies that promote the inclusion of these students into the class and within school activities. It is with these experiences, that the children would come to realise their strengths and weaknesses and develop an understanding of the impact of their disabilities on their academic, personal and social development (Most, 2004). Villa (1996) hence suggests that cooperative dealings among schools and Colleges of Educations is needed to help prepare teachers to accept and support students with special needs in general classrooms with modern and informative programme for teaching children with a Special needs.

However, Carrigan, (1994) is of the view that, even though most class teachers are in agreement with the general purpose of inclusion, they are pessimistic of the achievement of these objectives as they see it tough to do. Some teachers have concerns about teaching pupils with Special needs and they perceive limitations in its implementation. Similarly, (Mary, 2005) perceives difficulties in adapting instruction, meeting students' needs, and acquiring needed support. But Susan Shapiro-Barnard et al (1995) disagree with the above assertion with the view that, inclusion is very possible if different categories of children would be assessed differently and discard one-size-fit-all syndrome in our educational system (Susan 1996). Moreover, Bland ford (2006) substantiate the claim that class teacher's learn from day-to-day liaison with fellow teachers doing similar work with whom they can share expertise and also to modernize their professional skills in the key areas of special education, language development, communication and academic achievement techniques. To ensure that all students make progress and achieve rigorous standards, teacher candidates and those in the field must gain a sense of accountability as well as efficacy in teaching both the able students and students with disabilities (Gilmore and Cuskelly, 2003).

Teacher's attitude towards inclusive Education

Further, Golder et al (2005) were emphatic on the fact that, teachers should be encouraged to develop positive attitude to the education of children with special education needs in main stream schools and should be equipped with relevant knowledge and skills. Similarly, Stakes and Hornby (1998) concludes that there should be a special education course in all initial teacher education colleges so that teachers would develop positive attitude towards students with Special needs. Teachers' attitude towards special needs children is an essential element in the attainment of success in the attempts to include these children in general classroom.

Hence, Colleges of Educations courses need to change teachers' attitudes towards the acceptance of special needs students in their classrooms by broadening their knowledge in child diversity and teaching skills. Further, in-service teachers could be guided by resource teachers in the schools while they teach pupils with special educational needs in their classrooms (Sari, 2007). In the same vein, Frost and Stamp (1997) concludes that after teachers have INSET programme, most teachers would gain more confidence, realistic, positive and holistic conceptuality about students with special needs. Apart from attitudinal changes, the teachers would also become more compromising, capable and have techniques that they should use to help the students both inside and outside the classroom. The attitudes of the teachers have a significant effect on the attitudes of the pupils in the class; negative feeling toward special pupils can be communicated by the teacher (Simpson, 1990).

Research Question

1. How knowledgeable are the Tutors with regards to inclusive Education at Presbyterian College of Education?
2. What Teaching methods are adopted in an inclusive classroom at the Presbyterian College of Education?
3. What is the Tutors attitude towards inclusive Education at Pres by terian College of Education?

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The design is a case study in which tutors and students with special needs of Presbyterian College of Education Akropong were interviewed. Case studies involve empirical investigation of a particular phenomenon within its real context using multiple sources of evidences (Robson, 2002). The researcher settled on this design since he intended to undertake an in-depth study of the phenomenon in the real-life situation in order to unravel the actual perspective of the participants regarding inclusive education at Presbyterian College of Education.

Population and Sample Size

The study population comprised of all teachers and students with disabilities in the Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong. Overall, sixty (60) teachers and fifty-five (55) students with disabilities constituted the population. Creswell (2005) stated that a population refers to group of humans selected for a study. The sample size for the study was 15 tutors of the College and 35 students with disabilities was selected through convenience and census. Even though there were students with several forms of needs only those with visual, hearing and physical disabilities were included in the study. In the case of tutors all of them were qualified because they (tutors) all teach students with disabilities. Therefore, study participants were selected for interview until saturation was reached.

Instrumentation

The following instruments were used for the study; observation and interview

Observation

Observation of tutors and students in their activities during classes, break and college activities was conducted. Observing tutors during the classroom activities enabled the researcher to examine the kind of activities and interactions that go on during teaching and learning as well as dealing with material resource.

Observation was used because it enables the researcher to obtain information in its primary form, besides, observation put little or no pressure on the respondents. The observation also gives the researcher the opportunity to investigate things on the ground personally and to crosscheck the results with other instruments. Additionally, observation affords the researcher the opportunity of recording events spontaneously as they occur and provides data that relate to the typical behavioural situations. In the view of Macmillan and Schumacher (2007) observation has an advantage of the researcher not worrying about the limitation of self-reporting bias, social desirability, and the information is not limited to what can be recorded as it occurs naturally.

The observation was naturalistic using an observation guide to collect information on the following issues: location of school and physical environment, architectural design of building, material resources available and their efficiency, classroom activities, out of classroom activities and interaction between tutors and students.

Interview

In-depth one-on-one interview was conducted for tutors and students in the College. Robson (2003) stated that interviews typically involve a researcher, asking questions and hopefully receiving answers from people being interviewed. Although interview involves asking series of questions and following a procedure decided upon beforehand, the interviewer is largely free to arrange the form and timing of the questions. Also, the interviewer can rephrase the questions, modify them and add some new questions to the list (Robson, 2002).

The interview guide was in two sections. The first section specifically sought demographic data of respondents: gender, number of years of teaching, educational qualification and grade levels taught. In section two, the items sought information on how knowledgeable the tutors were about learners with special needs and how to educate them. The interviews were recorded by the researcher using audio tape recorder. In addition, important points raised by respondents were written down by my research assistant. Each interview lasted for 50 minutes. After the instruments were designed, they were read over several times to identify mistakes that might have been overlooked during the setting stage. Ambiguous items were restructured or deleted. To ensure validity of the findings, respondents' views, which was recorded manually, was read to them. This gave the respondents the opportunity to determine if their views were accurately recorded. Furthermore, the use of in-depth interview and observation in the study, allowed triangulation of the data. According to O'Donoghue and Punch (2003), triangulation is a method of cross-checking data from multiple sources to search for regularities in the research data. The use of triangulation in the research therefore increased the credibility and validity of the result.

IV. RESULTS

Finding from interview

Tutors knowledge on inclusive education at Presbyterian College of Education

Three major themes emerged with regard to tutors' knowledge about inclusive education: understanding the concept of inclusive education, teaching methods in an inclusive classroom and acceptance of the concept of inclusion and impact.

Understanding the concept of inclusive education

Analysis of the data revealed that most of the teachers currently have very limited understanding of the concept of inclusive education even though they have students with special needs in their classrooms and are supposed to be teaching them. The teachers interviewed further revealed that they did not have any idea of inclusive education before the College started the pilot inclusive education programme but the resource teachers and the Principal of the College respectively have some level of knowledge in inclusion. Some of the teachers involved in the teaching of children with disabilities commented as follows: "*We started practicing mainstreaming education fifteen years ago and I completed university of Ghana and so I have no idea about this inclusive education* (A male tutor, aged 46)." Another tutor also said that: "*We just started practicing inclusive education and don't know much about inclusive education.* (A female tutor aged 40)". Again another teacher mentioned that: "*No special education coordinator briefed us about inclusive education so we are novice when it comes to special education* (A female tutor, aged 50)".

However, the Principal of the College as well as the resource teachers reported to have undergone some training and claimed to be knowledgeable on inclusive education. The principal said: "*Yes I was given three weeks in-service*". The principal explained that: All principals of pilot inclusive Colleges in Ghana attended a training workshop on inclusion before their Colleges started the program. Similarly, the resource teachers claimed they had adequate knowledge about inclusion. A resource person at Presbyterian College of education stated that: "*I am more knowledgeable on inclusive education. I did special education and was introduced to inclusive education during my first degree. And I have been posted here to support regular teachers*". Another resource teacher remarked that: "*I have six years training on inclusion, a full time special educationist posted*

here to assist persons with disabilities especially those with visual impairments and hearing impairments so I am here to serve the purpose. (A male resource teacher aged 38)".

From the comments stated by the respondents it was evident that the general teachers(non-special educators) were not conversant with inclusive education before the commencement of the programme and little is done currently to update them on the concept. Even though there were a few resource teachers to assist, they are not always available to play their role because they are assigned subjects to teach.

Teaching methods in an inclusive classroom

Another important theme that emerged with regard to knowledge on the concept of inclusive education had to do with the methodology of teaching in an inclusive classroom for the benefit of students with special needs. The study showed that the teachers lacked the requisite teaching skills needed to teach in a class that includes students with special needs. Most of the teachers were of the view that they find it difficult to explain certain concepts to students with disabilities. One of the participants stated: *"it is very challenging to get a deaf student understand simple concepts in class; in fact we need to be educated on such methods."*(A male tutor aged 45)

Study participants expressed the view that being equipped with the appropriate teaching methods for an inclusive class would not only enable teachers to prepare lessons with informed inputs but also enhance full participation of the entire class. One female teacher expressed that: *"I have the desire to teach students with disabilities, all I need is the right methods to my planning and presentation of lesson."*(A male tutor, aged 36). Another participant stated: *"at times, I feel very sad and unfulfilled during classes due to the helpless state I find myself when it comes to explaining certain concepts to the visually impaired students."* (A female tutor, aged 58).

The views expressed by the participants indicated that having ideas about the methods of teaching in an inclusive classroom is required in such an inclusive institution. It becomes apparent the teachers required some form of assistance from the resource teachers to fill this gap.

Acceptance of the concept of inclusive education and its impact

Even though responses from the participants suggest that the tutors did not have enough knowledge about inclusive education before its implementation in the College of Education, some of them indicated that they accepted the concept after the Special Education officer met them and briefed them on the concept. As a result of the awareness created by the special education coordinator, some of them claimed their perception about disability has changed and became more tolerant to students with disabilities. For example, a teacher stated that: *"The policy has helped us to identify and appreciate the capabilities of persons with disabilities"*, while another teacher supported this assertion and said: *"Now I will be happy to chat, play and even to the extent of sharing ideas with a disabled student, one of the most difficult things I would have done without this inclusive programme"*.

The following comments further illustrate tutors' support for inclusive education. One teacher remarked that:

The program is good; I can't see anything wrong with this inclusive education program. Some of us who were initially against the policy and were distance from the disabled pupils due to our negative perceptions can now interact comfortably with the disabled pupils. Also we will encourage both the disabled and non-disabled students to play together because they now see themselves as brothers and sisters (a male tutor, aged 42)

Another teacher mentioned that: *"It has enabled us to understand these disabled pupils better than before because we now know some of their behaviours, the way they do their things as well as acknowledging and appreciating their needs which was not so at the initial stages of the inclusive programme in the school (a female tutor, aged 37)"*.

Comments from the teacher suggest that he was in full support of the policy and it has had greater impact in their life as well as educating them. A teacher said: *"The College principal was willing to accept students with disabilities because disability is universal and can affect anyone. And so it is wise to educate them and their peers in their local settings"*(A tutor, aged 40)". The principal also remarked that: *"This is government*

educational policy and College Principals are the implementers of such policies on the grounds so it is my duty as a Principal to ensure the success of the policy at least in my College here (the College principal, aged 57)”.

Similarly, comments by the resource person suggest that they had positive attitude towards the policy. Two resource persons explained that they supported the policy because unlike mainstreaming, inclusion has a lot of benefits for disabled students although they envisaged some difficulties in its implementation. The seemingly consensus among the respondents suggests that the inclusive educational policy appears to have been accepted by the College teachers, the head and the resource teachers although College teachers seemed to be unfamiliar with the policy.

Findings from the Structured Observation

In addition to the in-depth interview, a structured observation was conducted to supplement the findings from the qualitative interviews. The structured observation focused on how teaching sessions were organised by the tutors. The results from this aspect of the study are presented in the ensuing paragraphs:

It was observed that most of the teachers introduced their lessons without recognising the presence of students with visual impairment and those with hearing impairment. This was evident in the teacher's inability to verbalise every word on the chalkboard. Teachers were also observed speaking too fast during lessons without the recognition of the interpreter to give enough time for such students (hearing impaired) with special needs to make notes. Lessons lacked practical illustrations which may hamper understanding of the lesson by all students. It was observed that teachers failed to involve students with special needs in the classes by asking them questions and making them participate in activities. Also, adequate teaching and learning materials were absent in most of the lessons observed.

On the other hand, the observation also revealed that the teachers demonstrated an acceptance of the students with special needs. Very cordial relationship was observed in the manner in which students with special needs were welcomed at social gatherings such as church, dining sessions, sporting activities, and teaching sessions. The teachers were willing to offer little assistance when the need arises. Some teachers were observed walking along with students with special needs even with their hands around their necks. This is an indication that students with special needs are accepted by the teachers.

V. DISCUSSION

Knowledge on inclusive education at Presbyterian College of Education

The findings revealed that the teachers had a very limited understanding of inclusive education although they were aware of the existence of special school, and special needs children. This is in contrast to the assertion of Michigan (1991) and Golder et al. (2005) that there should be a special education need element in all courses of initial teacher training which will qualify them to understand their responsibilities with respect to inclusive education. This shows that all teachers were not familiar with inclusive education before its introduction in the College, suggesting that the implementation of inclusive education in the College was likely to face challenges. This is because understanding the concept by teachers is key to quality education and central to the success of inclusion. According to Ocloo (2002), teachers' knowledge of inclusive education increases their ability to provide modifications for pupils of diverse needs in the same classroom. As a result of lack of understanding of this concept, the teachers in the College do not know how to modify activities both outside and inside the classroom. This shortcoming leads to the alienation of students with special needs instead of inclusion. Inclusion is about participation and not the mere opening of doors of institutions to disabled students to school.

Teaching methods in an inclusive classroom

Again, as indicated by the findings from this study, teachers in this inclusive school of study lacked adequate methods of classroom management to practice inclusion due largely to inadequate preparation for inclusion. This is consistent with studies conducted by Minchon et al, (2003), Susan, (1996) and Bland ford (2006) who perceived difficulties in the classroom if instructors lack the sense of knowledge and skills in teaching children with special needs and knowledge of strategies that enhance the inclusion of these children into the classroom and within class activities. Most, (2004) explained that through the experiences of classroom

management, the students would come to appreciate their own strengths and imperfections which would increase their understanding of the impact of their challenges on their academic, personal and social maturation. Without adequate training and preparation, teachers would be less sensitive and responsive to the needs of children with special needs, which would in turn affect the participation and performance of the children. The importance of teacher preparation before the introduction of new educational policies was stressed by Hardman et al (2002) who argued that preparing teachers who will work with students with special needs require strategies, expertness, and knowledge that is simply indispensable. Rather, there is a need for such strategies, expertise, and skillfulness to be cautiously analysed, formulated and communicated so that the importance of the duties of the instructor would be more appropriately spotlighted and appreciated within the inclusive education schools. It is consistent with Avramidis et al (2000), and Cook et al (2000) who said limited information about students with special needs would lead to teachers fear, anxiety, and general discomfort in working with these students. Some of these behaviours result from a feeling of lack of preparation for teaching students with disabilities. Even though Villa (1996), Carrigan (1994), Sabbz (2008) and Mary (2005) perceived some difficulties in adapting instruction, meeting students' needs and acquiring support, Susan et al (1996) in contrast explained that inclusion is possible if different categories of students would be assessed differently and avoid one-size-fit-all kind of assessment.

Additionally, the findings of the study revealed that all the teachers were not briefed on what inclusive education is all about. The resource teachers as well as special education coordinator met teachers and learners as well as parents of students with special needs once and briefed them about admission of special needs children in Colleges of Education. It was established that most of these teachers could not explain what the inclusive education concept is, even at the time of study. This means, there is a gap between the implementers of the policy and teachers. Whereas (Sari, 2007), and Frost and Stamp (1997) found that after an in-service programme, teachers would acquire more affirmative, practical, and holistic view of children with special needs. Apart from attitudinal changes, the instructors would become more pragmatic and resourceful and have more skilful expertise that they would use to aid the children both inside and outside the school environment. The Special Education division of Ghana Education Service should have designed comprehensive upgrading programme of the Colleges of Education to avert this gap.

Attitude of Tutors towards inclusive education and its impact

With regard to acceptance of the concept and its impact on the teachers, findings revealed that most of the teachers liked the idea of having special needs students in their classrooms, although a few of them felt uncomfortable with the disabled pupils around them. This was evident in the way some of the teachers interacted with the special needs pupils when they felt no one was watching and the derogatory remarks they make about them. This is consistent to the claim of Golder et al (2005), Stakes and Hornby (1998) that teachers should do well to accept all students regardless of the condition because attitude towards special needs students is an important factor in the achievement of agenda to include students with special needs in general classroom. Thus, Colleges of Education courses should update teachers' attitudes towards the inclusion of special needs children in their classrooms by expanding their knowledge, strategies and instructing skills. Similarly, Simpson (1990) also believed the acceptance of special students through positive attitude have a significant effect on the attitude of the students in the class. The acceptance has impacted positively on both the teachers and the students in the sense that it has brought psychological relief to the teacher when teaching and it has also helped the teachers to discover the potentials of special needs students beyond their disabilities. The acceptance has equally relieved the special need students of the fear of rejection by the school community. So the students appear to feel comfortable to interact with teachers and their able counterparts.

VI. Conclusions and Recommendation

The study revealed that teachers in the area of the study do not have enough knowledge on the concept of inclusive education, though they accepted the concept. Findings also revealed that most of the teachers were in favour of having special needs students in their classrooms, although a few of them felt uncomfortable having pupils with disabilities around them. Additionally, it was revealed that teachers were inadequately prepared for

the programme. For example, they were not taught how to teach individuals with special needs. As a result, some teachers used teaching strategies that were unsuitable for the students with special needs.

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that the Principal should team up with the resource teachers to organize a day or two observations training for the general tutors to enable them handle students with disabilities at the college level. Consistent in-service training should be organized for the teachers by the special education division of Ghana education service to enable them manage the pupils with special needs in and outside the classroom. Again, Special Education programmes and workshops should be taken serious at undergraduate and master degree levels of training to equip prospective tutors with the requisite knowledge on special needs learners.

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